

IMPROVED FATIGUE CALCULATION OF ATTACHMENT WELDS IN OFFSHORE WIND STRUCTURES USING ADDITIVE MK FACTOR

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Secondary attachments are an essential part of any offshore structure. Typically these attachments are welded on to the primary structure, and therefore their fatigue performance impacts the integrity of the structure. While design of these details follows normal practice utilising S-N fatigue design approach, in many cases integrity management requires assessment of fatigue crack growth at these details, to quantify risk or develop inspection requirements etc. Fatigue crack growth of these welds typically follows the BS7910 or similar industry accepted standards. These represent the effect of the welded joints using an Mk multiplication factor. Small initial flaws tend to dominate the life of a welded joint, but this is where the Mk-factor is not well suited. This paper proposes an alternative approach which improves the calculation of this effect by considering an additive “Mk” effect rather than a multiplicative factor. This initial study gives a new method for determining the weld magnification effect which is a much simpler approach than the current method in BS7910. This has the potential to simplify the assessment of small flaws at an attachment weld toe.

Keywords: Fatigue, Mk factor, Attachment welds, Offshore wind.

INTRODUCTION

The life of offshore steel structures is commonly governed by fatigue of the welded joints, due to the cyclic loading from wave and wind action. Offshore wind is a significant growth area in the UK and worldwide. These structures have a particularly strong fatigue loading, since the turbines are designed to capture the wind load, and there is a strong cyclic content to the corresponding reaction loads carried by supporting structure.

Fatigue design is carried out using SN fatigue curves, and a plot from the current standard DNV-RP-C203 [1] is given below. The various steel fabrication details are grouped into categories of fatigue performance. For example Class B1 is for parent plate material, Class C for flush ground weld material, and Class D for a butt weld.

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FIGURE 1 S-N curves for fatigue assessment (from DNV-RP-C203, [1])

In some cases it is necessary to use a more detailed fatigue crack growth assessment, which uses the fracture mechanics based Stress Intensity Factor (SIF). For example, if cracks are detected in-service or from fabrication, or for reliability based inspection planning.

The fatigue life of a steel welded joint is commonly taken to be dominated by the time taken for an initial small fabrication defect to propagate by fatigue growth. A fracture mechanics based approach requires an initial defect to be determined. An equivalent initial crack size can be evaluated, such that the fracture mechanics based approach gives the same life as the SN fatigue life which is based on experimental fatigue test results.

In practice, these equivalent initial crack sizes tend to be lower than the small fabrication defects inherent in welds, which typically can be in the size range approximately 0.1 - 0.2mm or more. This means that there are other contributing physical effects apart from fatigue crack growth.

Nevertheless, it is useful in practice to follow the fatigue crack growth approach. One of the important contributors is the effect of the weld geometry on the SIF, and this is a strong effect for small cracks.

CURRENT CODE APPROACH

BS7910 [2] gives the current code guidance for fracture mechanics assessment of cracks in steel structures. For fatigue crack growth, the cyclic range of Stress Intensity Factor range (ΔK) is used in combination with the crack propagation law following Paris' approach (Paris, Erdogan [3]). The general formulation of SIF is as follows:

$$K = Y(a) \sigma \sqrt{\pi a} \tag{1}$$

K is the SIF

$Y(a)$ varies with crack size, geometry, loading type, etc

σ is the applied stress

a is the height of the crack

BS7910 provides solutions for $Y\Delta\sigma$ for a range of crack types and structural configurations. Of particular importance is the solution giving an amplification to the SIF value from the effect of the weld geometry, if a crack originates at the toe of a weld, which is a common occurrence, as shown below.

Hayes and Maddox [4] published early work which proposed an M_k factor to represent the increase in SIF arising from the proximity of the crack to the weld, as follows.

$$K_{Weld\ toe\ of\ Plate\ with\ attachment} = M_k K_{Plain\ Plate} \quad (3)$$

A diagram of the relevant semi-elliptical surface-breaking crack in a plain plate and at a weld toe of an attachment is shown in FIGURE 2 below.

FIGURE 2a) Plain plate b) Plate with attachment (from Pang et al, [7])

Various successive work was carried out by a number of researchers, and the work by Bowness and Lee [5] has been incorporated in BS7910. Their work was based on finite element analyses of cracks in welded attachments of a wide range of sizes and shapes.

A set of parametric equations was fitted to large range of many finite element analysis results. A plot of the resulting M_k factors is shown below in FIGURE 3, for one example case, with results for the deepest point and the surface point of the crack, and with applied membrane and bending stresses.

FIGURE 3 – M_k factor at an attachment weld toe, using equations from BS7910 [2].

Two limits on the parametric equations are given - M_k cannot go below 1.0, and an upper ceiling is given at a crack size of $a = 0.15\text{mm}$, to limit the value of M_k for cracks smaller than this. This is a pragmatic limit, and has been questioned by a number of people, including Mikulski & Lassen [8].

An extract from the parametric equations is given below (for the deepest point of the crack, with an applied membrane stress). Clearly the equations are rather involved, as might be expected from fitting a distribution with a high amount of curvature.

$$M_{km} = f_1\left(\frac{a}{B}, \frac{a}{c}\right) + f_2\left(\frac{a}{B}\right) + f_3\left(\frac{a}{B}, \frac{L}{B}\right) \quad (\text{M.44})$$

where:

$$f_1\left(\frac{a}{B}, \frac{a}{c}\right) = 0.43358 \left(\frac{a}{B}\right) \left\{ g_1 + \left[g_2 \left(\frac{a}{B}\right) \right]^{g_3} \right\} + 0.93163 \exp\left[\left(\frac{a}{B}\right)^{-0.050966}\right] + g_4$$

$$f_2\left(\frac{a}{B}\right) = -0.21521 \left[1 - \left(\frac{a}{B}\right) \right]^{176.4199} + 2.8141 \left(\frac{a}{B}\right)^{-0.10740} \left(\frac{a}{B}\right)$$

$$f_3\left(\frac{a}{B}, \frac{L}{B}\right) = 0.33994 \left(\frac{a}{B}\right)^{g_5} + 1.9493 \left(\frac{a}{B}\right)^{0.23003} + \left[g_6 \left(\frac{a}{B}\right)^2 + g_7 \left(\frac{a}{B}\right) + g_8 \right]$$

where:

$$g_1 = -1.0343 \left(\frac{a}{c}\right)^2 - 0.15657 \left(\frac{a}{c}\right) + 1.3409$$

$$g_2 = 1.3218 \left(\frac{a}{c}\right)^{-0.61153}$$

$$g_3 = -0.87238 \left(\frac{a}{c}\right) + 1.2788$$

$$g_4 = -0.46190 \left(\frac{a}{c}\right)^3 + 0.67090 \left(\frac{a}{c}\right)^2 - 0.37571 \left(\frac{a}{c}\right) + 4.6511$$

$$g_5 = -0.015647 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right)^3 + 0.090889 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right)^2 - 0.17180 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right) - 0.24587$$

$$g_6 = -0.20136 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right)^2 + 0.93311 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right) - 0.41496$$

$$g_7 = 0.20188 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right)^2 - 0.97857 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right) + 0.068225$$

$$g_8 = -0.027338 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right)^2 + 0.12551 \left(\frac{L}{B}\right) - 11.218$$

FIGURE 4 – M_k factors for membrane stress, at the deepest point of a crack. From [2].

ALTERNATIVE APPROACH - CONCEPT

The plots show a rapidly increasing M_k value as the crack size tends towards zero. However it is applied to the SIF for a crack in a plain plate, which decreases towards zero as the crack size tends towards zero. So the contribution to SIF from the weld geometry could actually be a modest and finite value. This is investigated first in principle (as proposed and evaluated by D Linkens [unpublished]), and is later followed up in more depth.

A simple approximation at first is given by the quantity $(M_k - 1) * \sqrt{a}$ which gives the extra contribution to SIF as the crack size tends towards zero (for unit values of stress and Y), as can be seen from equation 1.

FIGURE 5 below gives the results for the case that was taken, for the deepest point of a crack, using the M_k parametric equations as given in BS7910. It shows a stable increase in the effect of proximity to the weld toe, as crack size tends towards zero.

FIGURE 5 - $(M_k - 1) * \sqrt{a}$ for the deepest points of the crack, using equations from BS7910 [2]

Removing the dependency on $\sqrt{a}$ indicates that the asymptotic behaviour of M_k at very small crack heights may be due to dividing by a vanishingly small value of $\sqrt{a}$. It appears that the contribution to SIF at the weld toe tends to a finite contribution for very small cracks.

Incidentally, the reduction to zero at the left of the above plot does not seem to be appropriate. It results from the ceiling imposed at $a = 0.15\text{mm}$.

A closer examination is carried out by taking the original finite element analysis results that from Bowness and Lee [5] obtained. An example is given below in FIGURE 6.

Table A1
Mk database for the deepest point of the crack under membrane loading

L&P	a/T	a/c	θ	ρ/T	L/T	$Y_{plain\ plate}$	$Y_{Newman\ \&\ Raju}$	Mk	Mk from equation	Error (%)
ma	0.005	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.0349	1.1031	2.4457	2.4363	-0.4
ma	0.01	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.0809	1.1033	1.9874	1.9723	-0.8
ma	0.02	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.1032	1.1040	1.6220	1.6156	-0.4
ma	0.04	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.1413	1.1069	1.3447	1.3422	-0.2
ma	0.07	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.1526	1.1148	1.1808	1.1816	0.1
ma	0.1	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.1671	1.1270	1.1026	1.1034	0.1
ma	0.2	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.2516	1.1990	0.9805	0.9884	0.8
ma	0.3	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.4021	1.3202	0.9368	0.9324	-0.5
ma	0.5	0.1	45	0	1.25	1.8903	1.7175	0.8881	0.8644	-2.7
ma	0.7	0.1	45	0	1.25	2.4536	2.3401	0.8630	0.8405	-2.6
ma	0.8	0.1	45	0	1.25	2.6051	2.7455	0.8753	0.8634	-1.4
ma	0.9	0.1	45	0	1.25	2.5480	3.2202	0.9433	0.9471	0.4
ma	0.005	0.2	45	0	1.25	0.9979	1.0589	2.4149	2.4158	0.0
ma	0.01	0.2	45	0	1.25	1.0275	1.0590	1.9611	1.9519	-0.5
ma	0.02	0.2	45	0	1.25	1.0144	1.0595	1.5980	1.5955	-0.2
ma	0.04	0.2	45	0	1.25	1.0448	1.0614	1.2779	1.2779	0.0

FIGURE 6 – Example of the original Mk data given by Bowness and Lee [5]

It is appreciated that Bowness and Lee provided source data, since this provides an opportunity for further understanding and investigation. The original SIF (K) values can be reconstructed (for a unit applied stress and a nominal thickness of 25mm).

The SIF for a crack at the welded joint is then evaluated by multiplying $Y_{plain\ plate}$ by Mk. The resulting values of SIF are directly plotted below in Figure 6.

FIGURE 7 – Re-analysis of selected original data from Bowness and Lee [5]

The SIF for the crack at a weld toe (solid line) is higher than that for a crack in a plain plate (chain dash line). The difference steadily increases as the crack size tends towards zero, in a stable manner, and is shown by the dashed line, and is straightforward to understand, and also to implement. Using the results as a factor, by dividing one set of results by the other, is a less preferable way to handle this information, but has been customarily done for the M_k factor.

It is suggested that if the Bowness and Lee source data were available, it could be revisited in the light of these observations, and is likely to give a simpler and more insightful approach.

REANALYSIS OF ORIGINAL MK FACTOR WORK

Hayes and Maddox in 1972 [4] published an early paper giving a quantification of the increase in SIF at the weld toe, and a subsequent paper in 1974 [9]. Tabulated values of dimensionless results are given (Y and M_k) are given, for a range of crack depths and two weld angles, as shown below.

TABLE 1 Stress intensity factors for an edge-crack at the toe of a fillet weld

a/B	K/ $\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}$	
	$\theta=30^\circ$	$\theta=45^\circ$
~0	{ 2.016 1.800*	3.136 2.800*
0.050	1.280	1.407
0.075	1.286	1.369
0.100	1.287	1.345
0.125	1.296	1.340
0.150	1.313	1.349
0.175	1.339	1.370
0.200	1.372	1.400
0.225	1.412	1.439
0.250	1.460	1.487
0.275	1.514	1.541
0.300	1.578	1.615

*Excludes free surface correction term.

TABLE 2 Stress intensity magnification factors due to the weld toe stress concentration

a/B	M_k	
	$\theta=30^\circ$	$\theta=45^\circ$
~0	{ 1.80 1.61*	2.80 2.50*
0.050	1.15	1.27
0.075	1.10	1.20
0.100	1.08	1.16
0.125	1.07	1.13
0.150	1.06	1.12
0.175	1.05	1.11
0.200	1.04	1.08
0.225	1.03	1.06
0.250	1.02	1.04
0.275	1.02	1.02
0.300	1.01	1.01

*Based on solution for $K/\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}$ which excludes free surface correction term

When plotted, the M_k factors are as shown below.

FIGURE 8 – SIF magnification factors due to weld toe stress concentration (from [4])

By plotting normalised data, the effect of the weld geometry is somewhat obscured, and it would have been recognised more readily by plotting the SIF results directly.

The source SIF values have been reconstructed from these tabulated results (for a unit applied stress and nominal thickness of 25mm), and give the following plot.

FIGURE 9 – Reconstructed Hayes & Maddox 1972 data

The same observation is found, of a steadily increasing effect of the weld geometry as the crack size tends towards zero. The difference is plotted below, and allowing for variability which would be expected in the early days of computational crack analysis, an approximately linear relation is again given, consistent with the previous analysis of the Bowness and Lee data.

FIGURE 10 – Re-analysis of original Hayes and Maddox data as additive effect (data from [4])

FURTHER REANALYSIS OF OTHER BOWNESS AND LEE DATA (1999)

Some examples have been shown in the previous sections which demonstrate that the weld toe magnification effect may have merit to be considered as an additive effect, for one case, with aspect ratio $a/c = 0.1$. It is necessary to expand this assessment procedure to understand if this approach could be adopted for a wider range of cases.

A wider analysis of the Bowness and Lee data has been carried out. A selection of results are given below, showing additive contribution to SIF from the presence of the weld nearby.

FIGURE 11 – Re-analysis of original data to calculate the additive effect at the deepest point of the crack at the weld toe, all for 45 degrees case: (a) $L/T = 0.5$, (b) $L/T = 1.25$, (c) $L/T = 2$, (d) $L/T = 2.75$ (data from Bowness and Lee [5])

The above shows a consistent pattern, in accordance with what was previously found.

Thus, it seems that an additive contribution from the effect of weld geometry might be significantly advantageous compared with the present Mk multiplicative factor. It would give much simpler parametric equations, and provide more opportunity for physical understanding.

DISCUSSION

The results given in this paper show fairly straightforward trends in the effect of weld geometry on cracks at the weld toe. This suggests that a much more straightforward set of parametric equations could be obtained, by re-analysis of the source SIF data.

An important outcome of this work is that it shows a steadily increasing contribution from the weld geometry, tending towards a finite contribution to SIF as the crack size tends to zero. At first sight this has some alignment with the Hayes and Maddox work, who refer to the effect of a stress concentration factor at the weld toe, which implies a finite contribution.

A weld toe, if modelled with a sharp corner gives rise to a singularity rather than a finite stress concentration factor. This has been well researched over recent decades in the extensive work on notch mechanics. So a singularity without the presence of a crack is valid. The power of the singularity at a corner, however, is slightly lower than that of a crack, so there is not an exact match. For a weld with a 45° angle, the corner angle is 135°, and the power of the singularity is lower than -0.5, giving $1-\lambda = 0.326$ (Shen et al, 2015 [10]). The singularity is less pronounced, but the present proposal should be closer to the real situation than limiting the Mk factor to a ceiling at $a=0.15\text{mm}$, and thus gradually reducing the effect of the weld geometry to zero as the crack size tends towards zero.

To apply the additional contribution to SIF, the equation definition for the suitable additive term needs to be defined. It has to have dimensions of stress multiplied by length raised to the power 0.5. The length scale should not be the crack size, which would reduce the contribution to zero as the crack size reduces towards zero. Thickness seems to be a relevant length scale. A possible equation is given as follows.

$$K_{add} = M_{add}(a) \sigma \sqrt{t} \quad (4)$$

where $M_{add}(a)$ is the dimensionless parameter

A simple formula to calculate the bounding weld toe correction, might be possible. A simple suggestion based on the data shown in FIGURE 11 is as follows:

$$M_{add}(a) = 0.8 - 0.1a \quad (5)$$

This would need to be proved and refined, by processing the source SIF values, or SIF per for unit stress (since SIF can be reasonably taken as proportion for stress in a linear elastic situation), and to see whether the outcome of using the above equation gives a stable set of $M_{add}(a)$ results.

If successful, the resulting application to evaluation of SIF would then be :

$$K = Y(a) \sigma \sqrt{\pi a} + M_{add}(a) \sigma \sqrt{t} \quad (6)$$

It is noted that the contribution from the weld geometry becomes negative at larger crack sizes (FIGURE 11). This is probably due to the offset of the effective centroid of the cross-section when a weld is present on one side. In practical applications this benefit might not always occur, so it might be appropriate to limit M_{add} to prevent it becoming negative.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper gives an initial investigation into an alternative evaluation of the effect of weld geometry on a crack at a weld toe, a common case in practice. It shows that an additive contribution is likely to be much more suitable and straightforward than the traditional multiplicative M_k factor.

It is proposed that this be investigated further.

The authors invite the wider scientific community to share their source results, or process them along the lines of the approach proposed in this paper, to see whether an improved outcome can be achieved.

The ends of the crack, where it approaches the surface, also need to be considered. The work done to date shows that a different type of behaviour occurs, but it should be amenable to a similar approach.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

a – Crack height

B or T – Plate thickness

C – Crack length

K – Stress Intensity Factor

K_{add} – Additive weld toe effect on SIF

L – Length of attachment

Y – Shape factor

M_{add} – Additive weld toe effect (dimensionless)

M_k – Weld toe stress multiplication factor

σ - Stress

λ – Order of singularity for notch mechanics

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